

The Pictorial Representation of Social Milieu in Kamala Markandaya's Nectar in a Sieve

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Kamala Markandaya is a well-known and renowned writer of the twentieth century. She is a Revolutionary writer especially by focusing on the real-life of rural India. The grass-root analysis of Markandaya's work shows that she has an excellent knowledge of Indian rural life. The novel Nectar in a Sieve is her first novel in which a sincere attempt was made to project a pragmatic survey of rural India in all its shades and details – early marriage, dowry system, illiteracy, lacking in family planning, famine, drought, excessive rain, and struggle for survival, eviction, And superstition. There is a realistic description of a village which is symbolic of rural India.

It Depicts with vivid clarity and keen observation of social conditions of rural India. Individually, the terrible disgrace that human life brings is depicted with courageous realism. Markandaya spotlights the depression of the farmers realistically. They are desperate because of the vagaries of heartless men, the ruthless machines, the rampant hunger, and natural calamities. When an Indian village is on the threshold of industrialization, the peasant community suffers.

Both physically and mentally. Nathan and Rukmani are representatives of tenant growers in India and their life is an example of the mess caused by industrialization. Rukmani is the protagonist of the novel Nectar in a Sieve, has undergone many. Obscurities as a responsible Indian wife. She has been continuously entrapped and messed by The social setup which was followed by the ancestors of Rukmani. Being an educated daughter of the headman of the village, her family faced the hard times on her marriage which leads her to marry.

A tenant farmer, Nathan at her too young age. Though her husband Nathan is elder to her, his patience proves to be a loving person. Rukmani gives birth to the first child, a beautiful daughter named Irrawaddy, but for six Long years she fails to bear another child. Rukmani's husband wait for boy child so she secretly meets with western doctor Kenny who discharges his duties diligently and offers

her Treatment for infertility. Rukmani gives birth to five sons. Although, Rukmani and Nathan both Delight in their many children. Rukmani's family becomes a large one, so they search for a better salary job which must meet out the needs of the family.

Very soon, when a leather tannery opens in their village, things begin to change. People Are happy about the establishment of tannery unit which brings work and good pay. But the nearby villagers also influx to the area for doing a job which paves the way to hike the food prices. It makes the situation more difficult for Rukmani's family to feed her daughter and sons. In this The situation, Rukmani arranges the marriage for her daughter Irrawaddy. The suitor of Irrawaddy is Found by old Granny. They are delighted in finding a "good match" with a man financially Secure enough to care for her. At that time, they have had a good harvest, so both decide to Conduct the wedding. Unfortunately, that the same year the monsoon arrives earlier and destroys their crops which forced them to depend on their saved supplies, many of that were used at the wedding celebration.

The two eldest sons of Rukmani, namely Arjun and Thumbi now, in their early teen, work At tannery. Irrawaddy's husband returns their daughter to them because she cannot bear a child. In the secret, Rukamani pleads the western doctor to give her fertility treatment, but it is too late. Irrawaddy husband marries another woman. The boy's income at the tannery help to keep the Family afloat for a few years. To get rid of the trouble-making labors they organize a labor the strike which leads their family into more trouble, so they emigrate to Ceylon forever to work on a Tea estate. They do not have communication with the family. All these were happened because of Rukmani and Nathan's unawareness of family planning. The whole family continued to struggle. almost their family members are scattered. For the following year, the farmers encounter drought and the crops all wither and die.

The landlords also demand the tenant farmers to pay half of the rent for the land. Rukmani sells Even the cattle's to buy grains, but it is not enough. Starvation forces their family to forage Garbage and grass to eat. Due to poverty, Rukmani's third son Raja steals calfskin, he was Killed by tannery guards. Selvam, their fourth son, is the most educated person in the family who Works as an apprentice to the doctor Kenny. Rukmani's youngest son Kuti is suffered from poverty and so he was in dying state which forces Irrawaddy into prostitution.

One evening in a rage, Rukmani attacks Irrawaddy while she comes late to home. The family has no choice but to accept her new occupation. Kuti slowly recovers and soon his health Dies and deteriorates. Irrawaddy gives birth to an illegitimate child of Sacrabani. Though illiteracy prevail everywhere, Rukmani somehow succeeded in her life because of her rudimentary education and also her family members support.

The novel Nectar in Sieve highlights and unfolds many social issues which cause Rukmani's family to spread to various places and which makes all aware of social incapability and economic inadequacy and also kindle the inner heart of mankind.

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